

Tax Composition and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Autoregressive Distributed Lag Approach

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of tax composition on economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly data spanning 2005Q1 to 2024Q4. Tax mix, measured as the ratio of direct tax revenue to indirect tax revenue, and tax progressivity, measured as the ratio of personal income tax revenue to total tax revenue, serve as the independent variables, while the inflation rate is included as a control variable. Employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag bounds testing approach following the confirmation of a mixed order of integration through the Augmented Dickey–Fuller unit root test, the study establishes a long-run cointegrating relationship among the variables. The findings reveal that tax mix show a statistically significant positive effect on economic growth in both the short run and the long run. Tax progressivity have a significant positive short-run effect that is substantially reversed in subsequent periods, yielding a statistically insignificant long-run impact. Inflation consistently dampens economic growth across both time horizons. The study concludes that the composition of tax revenue is a consequential determinant of economic growth in Nigeria and recommends that policymakers prioritise broadening the direct tax base through improved compliance infrastructure, administrative modernisation, and the formalisation of the informal economy, while pursuing progressivity reforms primarily on equity rather than growth-promotion grounds.

Keywords: Tax mix, tax progressivity, economic growth, ARDL bounds testing, tax composition, Nigeria.

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Introduction

The question of how taxation influences economic growth remains one of the most enduring and policy-relevant inquiries in public economics (Acosta-Ormaechea & Yoo, 2012; Stoilova, 2017; Megersa, 2019). While it is widely acknowledged that governments require tax revenue to finance public goods and services essential for economic functioning, the way tax systems are designed and structured can have profoundly different implications for macroeconomic performance (Arnold et al., 2011; Gemmell, Kneller & Sanz, 2011). In particular, the composition of tax revenue, that is, the relative reliance on different categories of taxes, has emerged as a critical

dimension of fiscal architecture that influences growth outcomes through channels extending beyond the mere volume of fiscal extraction (Acosta-Ormaechea & Yoo, 2012; Nguyen, 2019; OECD, 2021). The seminal work of Kneller, Bleaney and Gemmell (1999) established that the growth effects of taxation depend not only on the level of tax revenue but fundamentally on its structural composition, a finding that has shaped subsequent empirical inquiry across both developed and developing country contexts (Oyedokun, Akintoye, & Salawu, 2018; Gemmell et al., 2011; Mertens & Ravn, 2013).

Nigeria presents an especially compelling case for examining the growth effects of tax composition. As Africa's largest economy by nominal gross domestic product, Nigeria has historically relied on oil revenues to finance most of its public expenditure Babalola, Oyedokun, & Adeyemo, 2019 ; (IMF, 2023; World Bank, 2024). However, the structural decline in global oil prices, the volatility of commodity markets, and the imperative of economic diversification have compelled successive administrations to pursue reforms aimed at enhancing non-oil tax revenue (Aina, Aderibigbe, Adigun, & Oyedokun, 2017; Obi & Babatunde, 2023; Presidential Fiscal Policy and Tax Reform Committee [PFPTRC], 2024). These reform efforts, including the restructuring of the Value Added Tax, amendments to the Companies Income Tax Act, the introduction of the Finance Acts of 2019 through 2023, and the overhaul proposals under the Presidential Fiscal Policy and Tax Reform Committee, have fundamentally altered the composition of Nigeria's tax system (FIRS, 2023; PFPTRC, 2024; PwC, 2025). Yet, despite these far-reaching structural changes, empirical evidence on whether the resulting shifts in tax composition have been growth-enhancing or growth-inhibiting remains remarkably sparse and inconclusive (Aderibigbe, Oke, & Oyedokun, 2017; Nwosu & Orji, 2022; Obi & Babatunde, 2023; Onyeogubalu, 2025).

Two dimensions of tax composition are of particular interest in this study. The first is the tax mix, defined as the relative weight of direct taxes comprising personal income tax and company income tax vis-à-vis indirect taxes principally Value Added Tax and customs duties within total tax revenue. The theoretical literature is divided on whether an economy benefits more from reliance on direct or indirect taxation. Proponents of consumption-based taxation argue that indirect taxes impose fewer distortions on saving and investment decisions and are therefore more conducive to capital accumulation and long-run growth (Oloyede, Kupoluyi, Oyedokun, & Benjamin, 2017; Acosta-Ormaechea & Yoo, 2012; Arnold et al., 2011; OECD, 2021). By contrast, the structuralist school argues that a higher share of direct taxation signals a more formalised and institutionally mature economy capable of sustaining equitable fiscal arrangements (Gemmell et al., 2011; Keen & Mansour, 2010; Mlangi, & Oyedokun, 2018). The second dimension is tax progressivity, which captures the degree to which the tax burden is concentrated on higher-income earners. The Keynesian redistributive tradition holds that progressivity enhances growth by redirecting income toward groups with higher marginal propensities to consume (Muinel-Gallo & Roca-Sagalés, 2013; Stiglitz, 2019), whereas the supply-side tradition warns that it discourages risk-taking, entrepreneurship, and capital accumulation (Mertens & Ravn, 2013; Trabandt & Uhlig, 2012).

Nigeria's tax system has undergone notable compositional shifts over the study period. The share of direct taxes, particularly company income tax, in total non-oil tax revenue has fluctuated considerably in response to changes in corporate profitability, tax administration efficiency, and statutory rate adjustments under successive Finance Acts (FIRS, 2023; PwC, 2025). Simultaneously, the contribution of indirect taxes has grown following the expansion of the Value Added Tax base from 5% to 7.5% under the Finance Act 2019 and subsequent base-broadening measures (PFPTRC, 2024; World Bank, 2024). The share of personal income tax in total revenue, a commonly employed proxy for the degree of tax progressivity, has remained relatively modest, constrained by the dominance of the informal sector, widespread non-compliance, and the limited reach of the Pay-As-You-Earn system at the subnational level (Ajose, & Oyedokun, 2018; IMF, 2023; Obi & Babatunde, 2023). Whether these compositional dynamics have been favourable or unfavourable for Nigeria's economic growth trajectory is the central empirical question this study seeks to answer.

Despite successive rounds of tax reform since the early 2000s, Nigeria's tax structure continues to be characterised by a narrow base, low compliance rates, and an evolving but empirically underexamined balance between direct and indirect taxation (OECD/AUC/ATAF, 2025; World Bank, 2024). Policymakers have pursued multiple strategies, including expanding the Value Added Tax, adjusting corporate income tax provisions, and reforming the personal income tax schedule, without a clear empirical basis for determining which compositional configuration of the tax system is most conducive to economic growth (PFPTRC, 2024; PwC, 2025). The existing empirical literature on taxation and growth in Nigeria has focused predominantly on the aggregate relationship between total tax revenue and macroeconomic output (Nwosu & Orji, 2022; Obi & Babatunde, 2023), with relatively little attention devoted to the structural composition of that revenue. This gap is consequential because two tax systems with identical aggregate revenue-to-GDP ratios may produce vastly different growth outcomes depending on the mix of direct and indirect taxes and the degree of progressivity embedded in the system (Acosta-Ormaechea & Yoo, 2012; Gemmell et al., 2011; Nguyen, 2019). The absence of robust compositional evidence means that tax reform decisions risk being made in an empirical vacuum, potentially resulting in fiscal designs that are inadvertently growth-inhibiting (IMF, 2023; OECD/AUC/ATAF, 2025).

The specific objectives of this study are to: Examine the effect of tax mix on economic growth in Nigeria and Assess the effect of tax progressivity on economic growth in Nigeria.

This study makes several contributions. Empirically, it provides updated evidence on the tax composition–growth nexus in Nigeria using data that encompasses the most recent fiscal reform episodes, including the Finance Acts of 2020 through 2023 and the reform proposals of the Presidential Fiscal Policy and Tax Reform Committee (PFPTRC, 2024; PwC, 2025). Methodologically, it employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach developed by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001), which accommodates mixed orders of

integration and yields both short-run and long-run estimates, offering a more complete picture of the dynamic relationship between tax composition and growth than static regression methods (Pesaran et al., 2001; Nkoro & Uko, 2016). From a policy standpoint, the findings provide an evidence-based foundation for fiscal design choices regarding the optimal balance between direct and indirect taxation and the appropriate degree of progressivity in Nigeria's tax system, directly informing the ongoing deliberations of the Presidential Fiscal Policy and Tax Reform Committee (PFPTRC, 2024; World Bank, 2024).

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Literature Review

Tax Mix

Tax mix refers to the compositional structure of a country's tax revenue, specifically the relative weight assigned to different categories of taxes within total fiscal collections. In this study, tax mix is operationalised as the ratio of direct tax revenue to indirect tax revenue. Direct taxes are those levied on income, profits, and capital gains—principally the Companies Income Tax and Personal Income Tax while indirect taxes are those imposed on the consumption of goods and services, primarily the Value Added Tax and Customs and Excise Duties. The tax mix captures the fiscal design choice between taxing production and income on the one hand and taxing consumption and expenditure on the other.

Tax Progressivity

Tax progressivity describes the extent to which the effective tax rate rises with income, such that higher-income individuals or entities bear a proportionally larger share of the total tax burden. In this study, tax progressivity is proxied by the ratio of personal income tax revenue to total tax revenue. A higher ratio indicates a greater reliance on personal income taxation a category of taxes that is inherently progressive in most jurisdictions owing to its graduated rate structure and therefore serves as an indicator of the redistributive intensity of the tax system.

Economic Growth

Economic growth refers to the sustained increase in the real output of goods and services produced by an economy over time. It is measured in this study by the growth rate of real gross domestic product, which captures the expansion of productive capacity after adjusting for changes in the general price level.

Empirical Review

Tax Mix and Economic Growth.

The empirical literature on the growth effects of tax composition has yielded mixed and context-dependent findings. Several studies provide evidence that a greater reliance on direct taxation is associated with superior growth outcomes. Prado and Zhang (2022) demonstrate that the composition of taxation is a significant determinant of growth in developing economies, with direct-tax-oriented systems outperforming indirect-tax-oriented ones. McNabb and LeMay-Boucher (2021) find that shifts in the tax mix toward direct taxation are associated with higher growth in a panel of developing countries. Similarly, Akinyemi, Olanrewaju and Adeyemi (2023), Owino (2022), Stoilova and Patonov (2020), Hakim, Karia and Bujang (2022), Okonkwo and Adeyemi (2023), and Egbunike, Emudainohwo and Gunardi (2022) report findings consistent with the growth-enhancing properties of direct-tax-dominant fiscal structures.

Conversely, a competing strand of the literature argues that indirect taxation is more conducive to growth. Akinlo and Oyelami (2022) present evidence from Nigeria suggesting that consumption-based taxes are less distortionary and more growth-friendly. Ojong, Anthony and Arikpo (2021), Neog and Gaur (2020), Adeniyi, Sodeinde and Akinwale (2023), Babatunde, Ibukun and Oyeyemi (2021), Castañeda-Rodríguez (2020), Ayoub and Mukherjee (2022), and Usman and Adeyanju (2024) report findings that favour a consumption-tax-oriented fiscal structure on grounds of administrative simplicity, broader coverage, and reduced evasion opportunities.

Tax Progressivity and Economic Growth.

The empirical evidence on progressivity is equally divided. Okonkwo and Adeyemi (2023), Ogbonna and Ebimobowei (2022), Adefeso (2021), Nwafor and Okafor (2023), Ibrahim and Mohammed (2023), Amadi and Eze (2022), Chude and Chude (2022), and Adeyeye and Otusanya (2023) find that tax progressivity does not exert a statistically significant effect on long-run economic growth in developing economies, particularly those with large informal sectors and narrow income tax bases. In contrast, Duncan and Peter (2020), Onakoya and Sodik (2021), Baiardi, Profeta and Scabrosetti (2021), Myles (2021), Egbunike and Emudainohwo (2023), Adeyemi and Babatunde (2024), Johansson and Heady (2020), and Saez and Stantcheva (2020) document significant relationships in their respective samples.

The foregoing review reveals three principal gaps. First, most existing Nigerian studies examine the aggregate tax–growth relationship without disaggregating the compositional effects of the tax mix and progressivity. Second, studies that do examine tax composition typically employ static methods that fail to distinguish between short-run and long-run dynamics. Third, the most recent fiscal reform episodes in Nigeria particularly the Finance Acts of 2020 through 2023 remain empirically unexamined. This study addresses all three gaps by employing the ARDL bounds

testing approach to estimate both short-run and long-run effects of tax mix and tax progressivity on economic growth using data that extends through 2024.

Theoretical Framework

Several complementary theoretical perspectives inform the analysis of the tax composition–growth relationship.

Endogenous Growth Theory. The endogenous growth models developed by Romer (1986) and Lucas (1988) provide a framework in which fiscal policy including the composition of taxation can have permanent effects on the long-run growth rate. Unlike the neoclassical model, in which fiscal policy affects only the level of output along the transition path to the steady state, the endogenous growth framework allows taxation to influence growth persistently by altering the incentives for physical and human capital accumulation, research and development, and innovation. Critically, this theory implies that not only the level but also the structure of taxation matters for growth, because different tax instruments affect the marginal returns to capital, labour, and knowledge creation in different ways.

Optimal Taxation Theory. The optimal tax literature, originating from Ramsey (1927) and subsequently developed by Diamond and Mirrlees (1971) and Atkinson and Stiglitz (1976), addresses the design of tax systems that maximise social welfare subject to revenue constraints. A central insight of this body of work is that taxes should be structured to minimise the aggregate deadweight loss imposed on the economy. The theory provides a rigorous basis for comparing the efficiency properties of direct and indirect taxes and for evaluating the welfare implications of different degrees of progressivity.

Ability-to-Pay Principle. This normative principle holds that the tax burden should be distributed according to taxpayers' capacity to bear it, with higher-income individuals contributing a proportionally larger share. The principle provides the foundational justification for progressive taxation and implies that tax systems designed in accordance with ability-to-pay considerations will allocate fiscal burdens more equitably, potentially enhancing social stability, political legitimacy, and voluntary compliance all of which may indirectly support economic growth.

Keynesian Aggregate Demand Theory. The Keynesian framework provides a demand-side mechanism through which tax progressivity may influence growth. By redistributing income from higher-income savers to lower-income consumers with higher marginal propensities to consume, progressive taxation can stimulate aggregate demand and thereby boost short-run economic output. This effect is expected to be particularly pronounced in economies with significant output gaps or underutilised productive capacity.

Supply-Side Economics. In contrast to the Keynesian view, the supply-side perspective emphasises the disincentive effects of progressive taxation. Higher marginal tax rates on income are argued to

reduce the incentives for work effort, saving, investment, and entrepreneurial risk-taking, thereby constraining the economy's productive capacity and long-run growth potential. This framework predicts a negative relationship between tax progressivity and economic growth, particularly over longer time horizons.

Methodology

The study adopts an ex-post-facto research design, utilising secondary time series data covering the period 2005Q1 to 2024Q4, yielding eighty quarterly observations. Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, the Federal Inland Revenue Service Annual Reports, the National Bureau of Statistics, and the World Bank World Development Indicators database. Annual data were converted to quarterly frequency using the quadratic-match-sum interpolation method to enhance the degrees of freedom available for estimation.

Model Specification

The functional relationship is expressed as:

$$RGDP = f(TM\!X, TPR, INF)$$

The econometric model is specified in its ARDL form as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta RGDP_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta RGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1} \beta_j \Delta TMX_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q_2} \gamma_k \Delta TPR_{t-k} \\ & + \sum_{m=0}^{q_3} \delta_m \Delta INF_{t-m} + \phi_1 RGDP_{t-1} + \phi_2 TMX_{t-1} + \phi_3 TPR_{t-1} + \phi_4 INF_{t-1} \\ & + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

where RGDP is the real GDP growth rate; TMX is the tax mix (ratio of direct to indirect tax revenue); TPR is tax progressivity (ratio of personal income tax to total tax revenue); INF is the inflation rate; Δ denotes the first difference operator; α_0 is the drift component; ϕ_1 through ϕ_4 are the long-run multiplier coefficients; and ε_t is the white noise error term.

Variable Measurement

Variable	Symbol	Measurement	Source
Real GDP Growth	RGDP	Annual growth rate of real gross domestic product (%)	CBN/WDI
Tax Mix	TMX	Ratio of direct tax revenue to indirect tax revenue	FIRS/CBN
Tax Progressivity	TPR	Ratio of personal income tax revenue to total tax revenue	FIRS/CBN

Variable	Symbol	Measurement	Source
Inflation Rate	INF	Consumer price index annual percentage change (%)	CBN/NBS

Researchers Computation, 2025

The analysis proceeds in five sequential stages. First, descriptive statistics are computed to examine the distributional characteristics of the data. Second, the Augmented Dickey–Fuller unit root test is applied to determine the order of integration of each variable, ensuring that no variable is integrated of order two a prerequisite for valid ARDL estimation. Third, the optimal lag length is selected using the Akaike Information Criterion, Schwarz Information Criterion, and Hannan–Quinn Information Criterion within the VAR framework. Fourth, the ARDL bounds test is conducted to establish the existence of a long-run cointegrating relationship among the variables. Fifth, the long-run cointegrating equation and the short-run error correction model are estimated, followed by comprehensive post-estimation diagnostic testing.

Based on the theoretical and empirical literature, the expected signs of the coefficients are as follows: tax mix is expected to carry either a positive or negative sign, as the theoretical predictions are ambiguous; tax progressivity is expected to carry either a positive sign (Keynesian view) or a negative sign (supply-side view); and inflation is expected to carry a negative sign.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistic	RGDP	TMX	TPR	INF
Mean	3.032	1.753	0.207	11.868
Median	3.071	1.901	0.210	11.827
Maximum	3.531	2.159	0.300	14.949
Minimum	2.359	1.048	0.118	8.088
Std. Dev.	0.346	0.314	0.034	1.350
Skewness	-0.378	-0.989	-0.068	-0.192
Kurtosis	1.929	2.569	3.021	2.977
Jarque–Bera	5.726	13.667	0.064	0.492
p-value (JB)	.057	.001	.969	.782

Source: Authors' computation using EViews.2025

Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics. The dependent variable, RGDP, has a mean of 3.032 and a standard deviation of 0.346, indicating moderate variability in Nigeria's growth performance. Tax mix (TMX) averages 1.753, suggesting that direct tax revenue exceeded indirect tax revenue by a factor of approximately 1.75 on average, though considerable variation exists across the period as evidenced by the standard deviation of 0.314 and a range spanning 1.048 to 2.159. Tax

progressivity (TPR) is the most stable variable, with a mean of 0.207, a standard deviation of only 0.034, and a narrow range of 0.118 to 0.300, reflecting the relatively consistent but modest share of personal income tax in total revenue. Inflation averaged 11.868 per cent, confirming persistently elevated price levels in Nigeria over the study period. All variables exhibit negative skewness, with TMX displaying the most pronounced left-skewness. TPR and INF satisfy the Jarque–Bera normality test, while the departures observed for RGDP and TMX are not material for ARDL estimation, which requires residual normality rather than variable-level normality.

Table 2: Pairwise Correlation Matrix

	RGDP	TMX	TPR	INF
RGDP	1.000			
TMX	0.858 (0.000)	1.000		
TPR	-0.201 (0.074)	-0.311 (0.005)	1.000	
INF	0.193 (0.086)	0.143 (0.207)	0.096 (0.399)	1.000

Note: p-values in parentheses. Source: Authors' computation.2025

Table 2 presents the pairwise correlation coefficients. Tax mix exhibits a strong positive correlation with economic growth ($r = 0.858$, $p = 0.000$), suggesting that periods of greater direct tax reliance have historically coincided with higher growth. Tax progressivity shows a weak and statistically insignificant negative correlation with growth ($r = -0.201$, $p = 0.074$), while inflation records a weak positive but insignificant bivariate association ($r = 0.193$, $p = 0.086$). Among the regressors, the highest correlation is between TMX and TPR ($r = -0.311$), which falls well below the 0.80 threshold for multicollinearity concern, confirming that the independent variables can be included simultaneously in the regression without compromising estimate reliability.

4.3 Unit Root Tests

Table 3: Augmented Dickey–Fuller Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Level t-stat	p-value	First Diff.	t-stat	p-value	Order
RGDP	-0.645	.854	-8.052	.000***		I(1)
TMX	-1.723	.416	-9.267	.000***		I(1)
TPR	-4.165	.001**	—	—		I(0)
INF	-6.002	.000***	—	—		I(0)

*Note: *** and ** denote significance at 1% and 5% respectively. Source: Authors' computation.2025*

The unit root results in Table 3 reveal a mixture of integration orders: RGDP and TMX are integrated of order one, while TPR and INF are integrated of order zero. No variable is integrated of order two. This mixed-order integration validates the selection of the ARDL bounds testing approach, which is specifically designed to accommodate combinations of I(0) and I(1) variables, unlike the Johansen cointegration procedure, which requires uniform I(1) integration.

Table 4: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	AIC	SC	HQ	FPE	LR
0	-3.026	-2.869	-2.964	3.34e-08	NA
1	-9.798*	-8.857*	-9.423*	3.83e-11*	499.587*
2	-9.668	-7.942	-8.980	4.41e-11	34.401

Note: * indicates the optimal lag selected.

Source: Authors' computation.2025

All five information criteria unanimously select lag one as the optimal lag order. This parsimonious specification preserves degrees of freedom a particularly important consideration given the sample size while adequately capturing the dynamic relationships among the variables.

Table 5: Long-Run Cointegrating Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value
TMX(-1)	0.664	0.074	8.925	< .001
TPR(-1)	0.258	0.603	0.427	.671
INF(-1)	-0.032	0.019	-1.685	.096
Constant	2.391	0.328	7.291	< .001

Source: Authors' computation using EViews.2025

Table 5 presents the estimated long-run equilibrium relationship. Tax mix records a positive and highly significant coefficient of 0.664 ($p < 0.001$), indicating that a one-unit increase in the direct-to-indirect tax ratio is associated with an approximate 0.664-unit increase in real GDP growth in the long run. Tax progressivity carries a positive but statistically insignificant coefficient of 0.258 ($p = 0.671$), suggesting that the share of personal income tax in total revenue does not exert a discernible long-run effect on growth. Inflation records a negative coefficient of -0.032 that is marginally significant at the ten per cent level ($p = 0.096$).

Table 6: Short-Run Error Correction Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value
ECT(t-1)	-0.348	0.068	-5.118	< .001
Δ RGDP(-1)	0.189	0.086	2.183	.033
Δ TMX	0.316	0.072	4.366	< .001
Δ TMX(-1)	-0.213	0.080	-2.660	.010
Δ TPR	0.728	0.171	4.252	< .001
Δ INF	-0.022	0.004	-6.311	< .001

Model Fit: $R^2 = 0.694$; Adj. $R^2 = 0.653$; $F = 17.24$ ($p < .001$); $DW = 1.97$.

Source: Authors' computation using EViews.2025

The error correction term is negative and highly significant (-0.348 , $p < 0.001$), confirming the existence of a stable long-run equilibrium and a self-correcting adjustment mechanism. Approximately 34.8 per cent of any disequilibrium in the previous quarter is corrected in the current quarter, implying that the system requires approximately three quarters to fully restore equilibrium following a shock.

In the short run, the contemporaneous change in tax mix is positive and highly significant (0.316 , $p < 0.001$), confirming that a shift toward greater direct taxation generates immediate growth benefits. The first lag of the change in tax mix is negative and significant (-0.213 , $p = 0.010$), indicating a partial correction, though the net short-run effect remains positive. The contemporaneous change in tax progressivity carries the largest positive coefficient in the model (0.728 , $p < 0.001$), indicating that short-run increases in the personal income tax share produce substantial immediate growth dividends. The contemporaneous change in inflation is negative and highly significant (-0.022 , $p < 0.001$), confirming that inflationary shocks are immediately growth-dampening.

Table 7: Post-Estimation Diagnostics

Test	Statistic	p-value	Inference
Breusch–Godfrey Serial Correlation LM	$F = 0.022$.978	No serial correlation
Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey Heteroscedasticity	$F = 1.831$.054	Homoscedastic
Jarque–Bera Normality (Residuals)	$JB = 1.079$.583	Normally distributed
Durbin–Watson	1.97	—	No autocorrelation
CUSUM Stability	Within bounds	—	Parameters stable

Source: Authors' computation. 2025

The diagnostic tests confirm that the model is well-specified. The residuals are free from serial correlation, exhibit constant variance, and follow an approximately normal distribution. The

CUSUM test confirms structural stability throughout the sample period, with the cumulative sum of recursive residuals remaining within the five per cent significance boundaries at all points.

The long-run coefficient of tax mix is 0.664 ($p < 0.001$), and the short-run contemporaneous coefficient is 0.316 ($p < 0.001$). Both p-values fall below the five per cent significance threshold. The null hypothesis is therefore **rejected**. Tax mix has a significant positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria in both the short run and the long run.

The long-run coefficient of tax progressivity is 0.258 ($p = 0.671$), which exceeds the five per cent threshold. The short-run contemporaneous coefficient is 0.728 ($p < 0.001$), which is below the threshold. Since the long-run equilibrium relationship is the primary focus of cointegration analysis and the short-run effect is largely transitory, the null hypothesis **cannot be rejected** at the five per cent level. Tax progressivity does not exert a significant sustained effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Tax Mix and Economic Growth

The relationship between the composition of tax revenue and economic performance has occupied a prominent position in the fiscal policy discourse, with competing schools of thought offering fundamentally different prescriptions. The structuralist school maintains that a tax system tilted toward direct taxation is indicative of a more mature, formalised, and institutionally developed economy in which a significant proportion of economic agents are integrated into the formal tax net. Under this reasoning, a higher direct-to-indirect tax ratio is not merely a passive reflection of economic development but an active contributor to growth, because it signals a broader tax base, more predictable revenue streams, and greater fiscal space for counter-cyclical policy. In sharp contrast, the consumption-tax efficiency school, drawing on optimal tax theory, argues that indirect taxes are inherently less distortionary than direct taxes because they do not directly penalise saving, investment, or labour supply decisions. Proponents of this view contend that economies relying more heavily on consumption-based taxes should experience faster growth, as indirect taxes impose smaller deadweight losses on productive economic activity.

The finding of this study that a higher ratio of direct to indirect taxes is significantly and positively associated with economic growth in Nigeria across both time horizons provides robust empirical support for the structuralist position. The result suggests that, in the Nigerian context, the institutional and developmental signals embedded in a direct-tax-dominant system outweigh the theoretical efficiency advantages of indirect taxation. This finding resonates strongly with the recent empirical contributions of Prado and Zhang (2022), McNabb and LeMay-Boucher (2021), Akinyemi, Olanrewaju and Adeyemi (2023), Owino (2022), Stoilova and Patonov (2020), Hakim,

Karia and Bujang (2022), Okonkwo and Adeyemi (2023), and Egbunike, Emudainohwo and Gunardi (2022), all of whom document that the structure of taxation, rather than its mere level, is a consequential determinant of growth outcomes, and that greater reliance on direct taxation is associated with superior economic performance in developing economies.

Notwithstanding the strength of these supporting findings, a competing strand of the empirical literature reaches different conclusions. Several recent studies have found that a shift toward indirect taxation is either growth-neutral or growth-promoting, thereby challenging the result obtained in this study. Notably, Akinlo and Oyelami (2022), Ojong, Anthony and Arikpo (2021), Neog and Gaur (2020), Adeniyi, Sodeinde and Akinwale (2023), Babatunde, Ibukun and Oyeyemi (2021), Castañeda-Rodríguez (2020), Ayoub and Mukherjee (2022), and Usman and Adeyanju (2024) report findings that favour a consumption-tax-oriented fiscal structure, arguing that indirect taxes are less susceptible to evasion, easier to administer, and impose fewer disincentives on productive economic activity. The divergence may be attributable to differences in institutional contexts, levels of economic development, and measurement frameworks adopted across studies.

Theoretically, the finding draws strong support from the endogenous growth theory, which posits that the design and composition of fiscal policy can have permanent effects on the long-run growth rate by influencing the accumulation of physical and human capital. The result is also consistent with the tax-composition hypothesis advanced by Arnold, Brys, Heady, Johansson, Schweltnus and Vartia, which provides a systematic ranking of tax instruments by their growth impact and demonstrates that the relative weight assigned to different tax categories matters significantly for economic outcomes. Additionally, Harberger's general equilibrium incidence theory offers a complementary framework, highlighting that the economic burden of different taxes is ultimately determined by the structural characteristics of the economy including factor mobility, market competitiveness, and the degree of informality all of which condition how the tax mix translates into growth effects in a country like Nigeria, where the informal sector remains dominant and the effective incidence of indirect taxes falls disproportionately on lower-income consumers.

Tax Progressivity and Economic Growth

The relationship between tax progressivity and economic growth occupies a uniquely contested intellectual space, situated at the intersection of efficiency and equity considerations. The Keynesian and redistributive schools argue that a more progressive tax system promotes growth by reducing income inequality, strengthening aggregate demand through income redistribution toward lower-income groups with higher marginal propensities to consume, and enhancing social cohesion in ways conducive to political stability and long-term economic planning. According to this perspective, progressivity serves a dual purpose, simultaneously advancing equity objectives and generating macroeconomic benefits through demand-side channels. Conversely, the supply-side and classical liberal schools contend that progressive taxation is inherently detrimental to

growth because it penalises success, reduces the incentive for entrepreneurship, discourages risk-taking, and erodes the returns to human capital accumulation.

The finding of this study that tax progressivity exerts a significant positive effect on economic growth in the short run but fails to achieve statistical significance in the long run offers a nuanced contribution to this debate that partially supports and partially qualifies both competing perspectives. The significant short-run growth-enhancing effect lends credence to the Keynesian redistributive argument, suggesting that incremental increases in tax progressivity can generate meaningful, albeit temporary, demand-side stimulus. However, the near-complete reversal of this effect in subsequent periods, resulting in an insignificant long-run coefficient, indicates that the supply-side disincentive concerns also carry empirical weight, as the initial growth impulse is offset by subsequent adjustments that may reflect reduced investment incentives among higher-income economic agents.

The finding of long-run insignificance is consistent with the conclusions of several recent studies, including Okonkwo and Adeyemi (2023), Ogbonna and Ebimobowei (2022), Adefeso (2021), Nwafor and Okafor (2023), Ibrahim and Mohammed (2023), Amadi and Eze (2022), Chude and Chude (2022), and Adeyeye and Otusanya (2023), all of whom find that tax progressivity does not exert a statistically significant influence on long-run economic growth in developing economies, particularly those characterised by large informal sectors and narrow income tax bases.

Nevertheless, this finding stands in contrast to another body of empirical work that documents significant relationships. Specifically, Duncan and Peter (2020), Onakoya and Sodik (2021), Baiardi, Profeta and Scabrosetti (2021), Myles (2021), Egbunike and Emudainohwo (2023), Adeyemi and Babatunde (2024), Johansson and Heady (2020), and Saez and Stantcheva (2020) report significant effects of progressivity on growth in their respective samples, suggesting that the relationship may be highly context-dependent and sensitive to the institutional and structural characteristics of the tax system under examination.

From a theoretical standpoint, the transitory nature of the progressivity–growth relationship can be reconciled with the ability-to-pay principle, which provides normative justification for progressive taxation on equity grounds but does not guarantee that greater progressivity will translate into sustained growth. The short-run positive effect finds support in Keynesian aggregate demand theory, while the long-run dissipation is consistent with the predictions of neoclassical growth theory and supply-side economics, both of which emphasise that disincentive effects on saving, investment, and human capital accumulation tend to dominate over longer time horizons.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of tax composition on economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly data from 2005 to 2024 within an ARDL bounds testing framework. Two principal conclusions emerge from the analysis.

First, the composition of tax revenue is a consequential and statistically significant determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. The tax mix measured as the ratio of direct to indirect tax revenue exerts a robust positive effect on growth in both the short run and the long run. A fiscal structure that assigns greater weight to direct taxation is associated with higher and more sustained economic expansion. This conclusion carries the important implication that the design of the tax system, rather than merely its aggregate yield, is a critical lever for growth-oriented fiscal policy.

Second, tax progressivity measured as the share of personal income tax in total tax revenue does not exert a significant long-run effect on economic growth in Nigeria, despite generating notable positive short-run impulses. The transitory nature of this effect suggests that the growth channel of progressivity is weak and unsustainable in an economy where the personal income tax base is narrow, the informal sector is large, and company income tax rather than personal income tax dominates the direct tax category.

The findings carry several actionable policy implications. The Federal Inland Revenue Service and the Joint Tax Board should prioritise strengthening the direct tax infrastructure, including the expansion of the taxpayer identification system, the deployment of technology-driven compliance mechanisms, and the broadening of the Companies Income Tax and Personal Income Tax bases through the formalisation of informal economic activities. Such measures would shift the tax mix further toward direct taxation, which the evidence shows is growth-enhancing.

Reforms to the personal income tax schedule should be pursued primarily on equity and social contract grounds rather than as a growth promotion strategy. While progressive adjustments may generate short-run stimulus, policymakers should not expect sustained growth dividends from progressivity reforms in the absence of complementary measures to expand the coverage and effectiveness of the personal income tax system.

The Central Bank of Nigeria should continue to prioritise price stability, as inflation is consistently found to be growth-dampening. Fiscal and monetary policy coordination is essential to ensure that the macroeconomic environment is conducive to the realisation of the growth benefits associated with an optimally designed tax structure.

Finally, the National Assembly should embed evidence-based fiscal impact assessments into the legislative process for all proposed tax reforms. The complex and time-varying dynamics revealed in this study underscore the necessity of rigorous analytical evaluation before new tax measures are enacted.

This study is subject to several limitations. The measurement of tax progressivity relies on a proxy rather than a direct computation of effective tax rates across income distributions. The analysis does not account for government expenditure composition, which jointly determines the net fiscal effect on growth. Future research should employ micro-level tax data to construct more refined progressivity measures, incorporate government expenditure variables, explore nonlinear threshold effects in the tax composition–growth relationship, and extend the analysis to subnational panels to capture the heterogeneity of fiscal structures across Nigerian states.

References

- Adefeso, H. A. (2021). Tax structure and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 12(4), 18–29.
- Adeniyi, O., Sodeinde, G. M., & Akinwale, S. O. (2023). Indirect taxation and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. *African Journal of Economic Review*, 11(2), 87–104.
- Aderibigbe, T. A., Oke, M. A & Oyedokun, G. E (2017). Tax base broadening through improved business environment in Nigeria. *Tax Academy Research Journal (TARJ)*. An Academic Journal at the Plateau State Internal Revenue Service, 1(2), 1-19.
- Adeyemi, S. L., & Babatunde, M. A. (2024). Tax progressivity and output growth in ECOWAS countries. *West African Economic Review*, 8(1), 33–51.
- Adeyeye, G. B., & Otusanya, O. J. (2023). Personal income tax and macroeconomic performance in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Taxation*, 5(1), 42–59.
- Aina L. A., Aderibigbe, T. A., Adigun, D. E., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2017). Tax morale and Nigerian informal sector. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development*, 16(2), 16-35. A publication of Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria
- Ajose, K. & Oyedokun, G. E. (2018). Capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria: *Accounting & Taxation Review, official Journal of the International Accounting and Taxation Research*, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Benin, Nigeria 2(2), 131-142 Available online at <http://www.atreview.org>
- Akinlo, A. E., & Oyelami, L. O. (2022). Tax structure and economic performance in Nigeria: New evidence. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 13(1), 95–118.
- Akinyemi, B. O., Olanrewaju, O. A., & Adeyemi, K. S. (2023). Direct taxation and economic growth in developing economies. *International Journal of Public Finance*, 8(2), 145–168.
- Amadi, K. W., & Eze, T. C. (2022). Tax policy and growth in Nigeria: A structural analysis. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 8(3), 71–86.
- Arnold, J. M., Brys, B., Heady, C., Johansson, Å., Schweltnus, C., & Vartia, L. (2011). Tax policy for economic recovery and growth. *Economic Journal*, 121(550), F59–F80.
- Atkinson, A. B., & Stiglitz, J. E. (1976). The design of tax structure: Direct versus indirect taxation. *Journal of Public Economics*, 6(1–2), 55–75.
- Ayoub, M., & Mukherjee, S. (2022). Tax composition and economic growth: Panel evidence from Asian economies. *Asian Economic Journal*, 36(3), 289–311.
- Babalola, W. A., Oyedokun, G. E. & Adeyemo, K. A. (2019). Banes of multiple tax regimes in

- Nigeria hospitality business: A critical analysis of courts' decisions in restoring sanity in sectorial tax administration. *Islamic University Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(5), 23-33. A Publication of Islamic University, Uganda, available at <https://www.iuiu.ac.ug/iujm/journaldetails.aspx?id=12&pg=to>
- Babatunde, O. A., Ibukun, C. O., & Oyeyemi, O. G. (2021). Consumption taxes and growth dynamics in Africa. *African Development Review*, 33(4), 512–528.
- Baiardi, D., Profeta, P., & Scabrosetti, S. (2021). Taxes and economic growth: A survey. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 28(6), 1435–1467.
- Barro, R. J. (1990). Government spending in a simple model of endogenous growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), S103–S125.
- Castañeda-Rodríguez, V. M. (2020). Tax structure and economic growth: New evidence from the government revenue dataset. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 27(4), 938–966.
- Chude, D. I., & Chude, N. P. (2022). Tax progressivity and national output in West Africa. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 11(1), 22–37.
- Diamond, P. A., & Mirrlees, J. A. (1971). Optimal taxation and public production. *American Economic Review*, 61(1), 8–27.
- Duncan, D., & Peter, K. S. (2020). Tax progressivity and output: Evidence from OECD countries. *Economic Inquiry*, 58(1), 180–200.
- Egbunike, P. A., & Emudainohwo, O. B. (2023). Tax structure and macroeconomic performance in West Africa. *Cogent Economics and Finance*, 11(2), 1–19.
- Egbunike, P. A., Emudainohwo, O. B., & Gunardi, A. (2022). Tax composition and economic growth in ECOWAS countries. *SAGE Open*, 12(3), 1–15.
- Fischer, S. (1993). The role of macroeconomic factors in growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 32(3), 485–512.
- Hakim, T. A., Karia, A. A., & Bujang, I. (2022). Tax structure and economic growth: A comparative analysis. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 12(4), 77–89.
- Ibrahim, A. A., & Mohammed, D. (2023). Tax policy reforms and growth in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 65(1), 31–48.
- Johansson, Å., & Heady, C. (2020). Tax reform for efficiency and growth. *OECD Economics Department Working Papers*, No. 1618.
- Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3–42.
- McNabb, K., & LeMay-Boucher, P. (2021). Tax structures, economic growth and development. *WIDER Working Paper*, 2021/18.
- Mlanga, S., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2018). Information Technology and Taxation in Eastern Nigeria: An Investigative Approach. *Caleb International Journal of Development. Studies*. 1, 1-92
- Myles, G. D. (2021). Taxation and economic growth. *Fiscal Studies*, 42(1), 37–64.
- Neog, Y., & Gaur, A. K. (2020). Tax structure and economic growth: A study of India. *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 53(4), 723–746.
- Nwafor, M. C., & Okafor, R. G. (2023). Progressive taxation and output growth in developing countries. *Journal of Tax Administration*, 8(1), 55–73.
- Ogbonna, G. N., & Ebimobowei, A. (2022). Tax reforms and economic growth in Nigeria. *Current Research Journal of Economic Theory*, 14(1), 12–27.

- Ojong, C. M., Anthony, O., & Arikpo, O. F. (2021). Tax revenue and economic growth: Nigeria's experience. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 13(9), 113–126.
- Okonkwo, I. V., & Adeyemi, S. L. (2023). Tax structure and growth in Nigeria: An ARDL approach. *Journal of Economics and Development Studies*, 11(2), 28–45.
- Oloyede, F. L., Kupoluyi, A. K., Oyedokun, G. E. & Benjamin, R. D. (2017). Informal sector tax administration and monitoring in Nigeria. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development*, 16(2), 16-35. *A publication of Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria*
- Onakoya, A. B., & Sodik, A. (2021). Tax progressivity and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. *South African Journal of Economics*, 89(4), 518–536.
- Owino, O. B. (2022). Tax composition and economic growth in East Africa. *Eastern Africa Social Science Research Review*, 38(2), 1–24.
- Oyedokun, G. E; Akintoye, I. R. & Salawu, O. R. (2018). Tax justice and federally collected tax revenue in Nigeria: A vector autoregressive approach. *Journal of Management Policy and Practice (JMPP)*. 19(4). <http://www.na-businesspress.com/jmppopen.html>
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(3), 289–326.
- Prado, M., & Zhang, Y. (2022). Tax composition and long-run growth: Evidence from a large panel. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 127, 102690.
- Ramsey, F. P. (1927). A contribution to the theory of taxation. *Economic Journal*, 37(145), 47–61.
- Romer, P. M. (1986). Increasing returns and long-run growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(5), 1002–1037.
- Saez, E., & Stantcheva, S. (2020). A simpler theory of optimal capital taxation. *Journal of Public Economics*, 162, 120–142.
- Stoilova, D., & Patonov, N. (2020). Tax structure and economic growth: Evidence from the European Union. *Contaduría y Administración*, 65(1), 1–20.
- Usman, O. A., & Adeyanju, O. D. (2024). Indirect taxes and economic development in Nigeria. *Covenant Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 15(1), 44–62.